

D6.5

Final Data Management Plan

Project Name	Piloting open and responsible Activities and Trainings Towards the Enhancement of Researchers Networks
Project Acronym	PATTERN
Contract No.	101094416
Type of action	HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01: Widening participation and strengthening the European Research Area centres
Topic	HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-44: Developing and piloting training on the practice of open and responsible research and innovation
Start of Project	1 January 2023
Duration	42 months

OUR CONSORTIUM

Deliverable title	Final Data Management Plan
Deliverable number	D6.5
Deliverable version	3.0
Previous version(s)	1.0 (D6.3), 2.0 (D6.4)
Contractual date of delivery	31 December 2025
Actual date of delivery	22 December 2025
Nature of deliverable	DMP
Dissemination level	PU - Public
Work Package	WP6
Task(s)	T6.3
Partner responsible	APRE
Author(s)	Alessio Livio Spera
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.18019532

Copyright

 Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY)

This document is released under the Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) license, which allows for the free use, distribution, and adaptation of the work, provided proper attribution is given to the original author(s). By accessing or using this report, you acknowledge and agree to comply with the terms and conditions of the CC-BY license. For the full text of the license, please visit: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode>

Contributors

NAME	ORGANISATION
Gitte Kragh	AU
Ioana Bara-Busila	ESF
Asya Salnikova	ESF
Pietro Rigonat	LOBA
Muki Haklay	LPI
Eric Cherel	LPI
Theodora Kavvadia	OpenAIRE
Katharina Koller	ZSI
Ilse Marschalek	ZSI

Peer Reviews

NAME	ORGANISATION
Michelle van den Berk	DANS

Revision History

VERSION	DATE	REVIEWER	MODIFICATIONS
0.1	17/04/2023	Claudia Iasillo (APRE)	First Draft
0.2	25/04/2023	Alessio Livio Spera (APRE), Pietro Rigonat (LOBA), Asya Salnikova (ESF), Eric Cherel (LPI), Jonathan England, Elli Papadopoulou, Venkataraman Shanmugasundaram (OpenAIRE), Marco Soriano (UNISR), Pascal Flohr (KNAW)	Comments from partners
1.0	28/04/2023	Claudia Iasillo	<u>Version submitted</u>
1.1	10/06/2024	Alessio Livio Spera (APRE)	First Draft of the Second DMP
1.2	25/06/2024	Cristina Lagido (AU), Asya Salnikova (ESF), Adam Brandstetter-Kunc (ESF), Eric Cherel (LPI), Katharina Koller (ZSI), Theodora Kavvadia (OpenAIRE)	Comments from partners

2.0	28/06/2024	Alessio Livio Spera (APRE)	<u>Version submitted</u>
2.1	13/11/2025	Alessio Livio Spera (APRE)	First Draft of the Final DMP
2.2	09/12/2025	Gitte Kragh (AU), Muki Haklay (LPI), Eric Cherel (LPI), Ioana Bara-Busila (ESF), Asya Salnikova (ESF), Pietro Rigonat (LOBA), Katharina Koller (ZSI), Ilse Marschalek (ZSI), Theodora Kavvadia (OpenAIRE)	Comments and contributions from partners
3.0	22/12/2025	Alessio Livio Spera (APRE)	Version submitted

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
AU	Aarhus University
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution
CS	Citizen Science
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ERA	European Research Area
ESF	European Science Foundation
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Accessible
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEIs	Higher Education Institution
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LC	Learning Cycle
LLM	Large Language Model
LMS	Learning Management System
LOBA	Globaz, S.A.
LPI	Learning Planet Institute
M	Month
MCP	Model Context Protocol
MLE	Mutual Learning Exercise
OA	Open Access
OpenAIRE	OPENAIRE AMKE
OS	Open Science
PU	Public
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SCORM	Shareable Content Object Reference Model
T	Task
WP	Work Package
ZSI	Zentrum fur Soziale Innovation

Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	8
2. Introduction.....	9
2.1 Background: PATTERN project.....	9
2.2 Objectives and logic of PATTERN Final DMP	9
3. Updates compared to the second DMP	11
4. PATTERN Datasets	13
4.1 Trainings mapping dataset.....	16
4.1.1 Trainings mapping dataset reusability after the end of the project.....	16
4.2 MLEs dataset.....	16
4.2.1 MLEs dataset reusability after the end of the project	17
4.3 Training modules dataset	17
4.3.1 Training modules dataset reusability after the end of the project	18
4.4 Platforms dataset	18
4.4.1 Platforms dataset reusability after the end of the project	20
4.5 Training plans dataset	20
4.5.1 Training plans dataset reusability after the end of the project	21
4.6 Piloting dataset	21
4.6.1 Piloting dataset reusability after the end of the project.....	22
4.7 Evaluation: facilitator reflection dataset	22
4.7.1 Evaluation: facilitator reflection dataset reusability after the end of the project	23
4.8 Evaluation: participant questionnaire dataset	23
4.8.1 Evaluation: participant questionnaire dataset reusability after the end of the project	23
4.9 Evaluation: Interviews with pilot institutions	23
4.9.1 Evaluation: Interviews with pilot institutions dataset reusability after the end of the project.....	24
4.10 Policy mapping dataset.....	24
4.10.1 Policy mapping dataset reusability after the end of the project	25
4.11 Dissemination dataset.....	25
4.11.1 Dissemination dataset reusability after the end of the project	26
4.12 Management dataset	26
4.12.1 Management dataset reusability after the end of the project	27
5. Conclusions.....	28

List of Tables

Table 1 - Significant changes to WPs' data lifecycles compared to the second DMP... 11	
Table 2 - PATTERN datasets summary	14

1. Executive Summary

The current document, titled "**PATTERN Final Data Management Plan**" (D6.5), represents the definitive update on data management strategies for the **PATTERN** project (**Grant Agreement No 101094416**).

While the first version (D6.3) established the theoretical framework and FAIR principles, and the second version (D6.4) mapped the initial emergence of datasets at M18, this final version focuses on the **consolidation, preservation, and reusability** of the data generated throughout the project's lifecycle.

With the project approaching its conclusion, this document moves beyond the general data management procedures, which remain valid as defined in previous versions, to provide a granular analysis of the **12 consolidated datasets**. This includes the addition of a dedicated dataset for qualitative evaluation interviews (see 4.9), ensuring comprehensive coverage of all data types generated. Special emphasis is placed on their long-term sustainability, specifying for each dataset the repository used, the licensing applied, and the concrete possibilities for reuse by third parties after the end of the action.

2. Introduction

2.1 Background: PATTERN project

PATTERN is a Coordination and Support Action whose aim is to promote the practice of Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (Open RRI) by developing and piloting training activities for researchers at all stages of their careers.

While research institutions and universities have always paid a lot of attention to trainings that build technical and scientific competences of their researchers' workforce, only recently they have better embraced their institutional responsibility in supporting the professional development of researchers beyond academia, by investing resources in offering researchers advanced trainings on more transversal and generic skills (**transferable skills**). PATTERN trainings strengthen researchers' ORRI transferable skills, with the ultimate goal to empower higher education institutions and research organizations to embrace a transformative process to improve the excellence of the science conducted, the capacity within the European Research Area (ERA) to tackle societal challenges and the interaction between science and society.

PATTERN focuses on defining a set of training materials and activities on transferable skills within the ORRI framework. Eight main transferable skills have been identified: Open Access (OA); FAIR data management; Citizen Science (CS); Research Integrity (RI); Gender, Non-discrimination and Inclusion in research (GNI); Dissemination and Exploitation of results (D&E); Science Communication (towards media and policymakers) (SC); Management and Leadership (including Mental Health) (MHL). For each of them, specific training modules were developed and tested in 14 Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), namely Pilot Organizations, and made publicly accessible on the PATTERN digital ecosystem (composed of the Projects platform and OpenPlato). Moreover, PATTERN addresses authorities responsible for researcher training, presenting evidence-based recommendations on educational policies to empower HEIs in contributing to bridge the gap between science and society.

2.2 Objectives and logic of PATTERN Final DMP

This deliverable serves as the third and final iteration of the Data Management Plan. Given the mature stage of the project (M36), this document adopts a targeted approach: instead of reiterating the general data management protocols (e.g., naming conventions, storage security, personal data protection) defined in D6.3 and confirmed in D6.4, it focuses entirely on the **inventory of generated data** and their **future usability**.

Therefore, the previous guidelines regarding the *PATTERN Data Lifecycle* and *FAIR Data implementation* remain fully operative but are referenced here only implicitly. The consortium's commitment to those principles stands firm.

The primary objective of this Final DMP is to act as a **comprehensive registry of project results**. It aims to:

- Update the status of the datasets mapped at M18, highlighting any significant deviations (Updates compared to the second DMP);
- Detail the final composition of the 12 datasets (PATTERN Datasets);
- Define the "Exit Strategy" for each dataset, explicitly addressing how they can be accessed and reused by the scientific community and the public after the project ends, and sustainably stored for the long-term.

Consequently, the document is structured to guide the reader from the recent updates directly into the deep dive of each dataset, serving as a practical guide for future data re-users.

3. Updates compared to the second DMP

Since the submission of the Second DMP at M18, the data management landscape of PATTERN has evolved to adapt to the project's practical implementation. The updates listed below reflect not only corrective measures (e.g., adjustments in data size estimation) but also strategic decisions aimed at maximizing impact, such as the shift to open-source licensing for the platform code.

The following table outlines the substantial changes to the data lifecycles.

Table 1 - Significant changes to WPs' data lifecycles compared to the second DMP

WP	Affected field, aspect, or category	Description
2	Data access	Strategic collaborations with major universities (e.g., Panthéon-Sorbonne, Sorbonne University) have been established. These institutions now contribute significantly to the platform's code and its long-term evolution, enhancing sustainability.
3	Data access / Size of data	Maturation of Training and Piloting Data: Datasets related to training modules (WP2) and piloting activities (WP3) have reached an advanced stage. While training modules are now fully accessible (see 4.3), piloting data accessibility remains partially restricted based on the data's nature (e.g., public session outputs vs. internal monitoring, see 4.6). This maturity allows for a definitive assessment of their current size and a refined estimation for M42.
	Data classification / New dataset	Inclusion of qualitative evaluation data: To provide a deeper institutional perspective on the training piloting, a new activity consisting of qualitative interviews with pilot representatives was conducted. This generated a new, distinct stream of data (recordings and non-anonymous transcripts) compared to the quantitative surveys. Consequently, a 12th dataset (<i>Evaluation: Interviews with pilot institutions</i>) has been formally introduced to manage this specific content.
4	Data access	Integration into Deliverables: The core content and value of the policy grids and reports have been fully integrated into the public deliverables of WP4 (specifically D4.1 and D4.2). Consequently, the raw internal datasets are considered superseded by these public documents.
5	Size of data	Re-estimation due to Activity Volume: The volume was significantly underestimated at M18. Due to the exponential increase in dissemination activities carried out by the consortium, previous projections have been exceeded. The revised estimate for M42 is approximately 5GB.

6	Size of data	<p>Refinement of Projections: The volume was overestimated at M18. With only six months of project implementation remaining, a more accurate projection is possible. The final estimate for M42 has been adjusted to 45GB.</p>
	Data access	<p>Integration as EU Project Community: PATTERN submitted a request to join as a subcommunity of the EU Open Research Repository on Zenodo, to strengthen collaboration, ensure stronger compliance, increase integration, gain additional visibility and impact¹.</p>

¹ The request has been formally submitted at the time of writing the present document (December 2025), therefore it has not been accepted yet.

4. PATTERN Datasets

Throughout the project's lifecycle, the consortium has continuously monitored data generation across all Work Packages, adhering to the tracking procedures established in the previous versions of the DMP.

As the project approaches its conclusion (M36), the focus of data management shifts from daily processing to long-term sustainability. The datasets initially identified in the Second DMP have been fully consolidated and refined. Furthermore, a specific dataset dedicated to qualitative evaluation has been isolated to better manage sensitive interview data, bringing the total count to **12 datasets**. This chapter provides their definitive specification.

Table 2 offers an updated summary of these datasets. The subsequent sections analyze each of them in depth, with a primary focus on their "**Exit Strategy**". Specifically, for each dataset, details are provided regarding the concrete measures implemented to ensure its preservation and, where applicable, its reusability by the scientific community and the public after the end of the grant.

Table 2 - PATTERN datasets summary

DATASET NAME	PARTNER	SOURCE	SIZE	TASK	ACCESSIBILITY
Trainings_mapping	AU	Existing, generated	650 KB + 475 KB ²	T1.1, T1.3	Integrated into D1.1 (dissemination level: PU), into one published publication and into another submitted publication
MLEs	ZSI	Generated	2.5 GB	T1.2	Aggregated information is provided in D1.1 (dissemination level: PU) to protect participants' personal information
Training_modules	OpenAIRE /LPI	Generated	1 GB ³	T2.1	All training materials will be digitized and available on the project's website for open access. Users can access materials via the website or digital Ecosystem, organized by relevant categories and fully indexed by a search engine. Furthermore, to enhance sustainability of long-term access, especially for static resources, uploading to Zenodo is already ongoing/planned for some thematic areas, and will be recommended as main sustainability solution for all suitable resources until the end of the project.
Platform	LPI	User generated	80 MB	T2.2, T2.3	Accessible through APIs, visibility controlled by data owner
Training_plans	OpenAIRE	Generated	5 MB ⁴	T3.1	Detailed description provided in D3.2 (dissemination level: PU)
Piloting	OpenAIRE	Generated	5 MB ⁵	T3.2	The ongoing process is provided through monitoring tools
Evaluation_facilitator_reflection	ZSI	Generated	4 KB	T3.3	Responses to the template for facilitators may not be anonymous and will not be uploaded to a data repository. Aggregated information will be provided in T3.3 deliverables (D3.3, D3.4)

² UPDATED: the two different figures reflect the size of the dataset on both the project's SharePoint and Zenodo community.

³ UPDATED: estimated size by M42 now introduced.

⁴ UPDATED: data source and estimated size by M42 now introduced.

⁵ UPDATED: data source and estimated size by M42 now introduced.

Evaluation_participant_questionnaire	ZSI	Generated	23 KB	T3.3	All responses to the anonymous evaluation questionnaire will be uploaded to Zenodo by the end of T3.3 as a .csv file
Evaluation_interviews_with_pilot_institutions⁶	ZSI	Generated	2.5 GB	T3.3	Responses to the evaluation interviews may not be anonymous and will not be uploaded to a data repository. Aggregated analysis of interview transcripts will be provided in T3.3 deliverable (D3.4)
Policy_mapping	ESF	Existing	2.7 MB	T4.1	Integrated into D4.1 (dissemination level: PU), published January 2023 and D4.2 (dissemination level: PU), published April 2024
Dissemination	LOBA	Generated	5GB ⁷	T5.1	Templates and source files are restricted to consortium; all other materials (posters, booklets, infographics, presentations, etc.) are publicly available for communication and dissemination purposes
Management	APRE	Generated	41 GB ⁸	T6.1, T6.2, T6.3	Restricted to consortium

⁶ NEW DATASET deriving from an additional evaluation action implemented in the second Learning Cycle.

⁷ UPDATED: new estimated size by M42.

⁸ UPDATED: new estimated size by M42.

4.1 Trainings mapping dataset

Under WP1, AU, with the help of consortium partners, mapped existing training materials, both publicly available and those with restricted access relevant to all eight Open RRI focus areas in any language, to be used as basis for gap analysis. Results were consolidated in the deliverable D1.1 (*Report on the Analysis of Existing Training Activities and Quality Assessment*).

Aspect	Description
Data origin	Publicly available data and project partners' knowledge of relevant trainings
Main data types	Excel mapping spreadsheet with detailed information on known training materials
Purpose of data collection	Basis for analysis of existing training materials and identification of relevant training gaps for PATTERN to fill
Format and storage	.xlsx file stored in the project repository on SharePoint. Also publicly available on Zenodo ⁹
Data management	Openly available on Zenodo
Reuse and sharing	Shared on Zenodo and openly available for anyone to use

4.1.1 Trainings mapping dataset reusability after the end of the project

As the dataset is openly available on Zenodo, anyone could use it as they see fit. In time, the dataset will become out-of-date as it will not be updated, but it could still be a useful reference list of Open RRI trainings.

4.2 MLEs dataset

A shared Excel file hosted on SharePoint was used in WP1 to compile and manage contact information for potential experts. The project partners contributed entries based on their own networks and additional desk research to ensure coverage across relevant sectors and, in the case of the third MLE, adequate geographic representation. The list served solely as an internal tool to support the selection and invitation of experts.

Aspect	Description
Data origin	Data of Stakeholders invited to Mutual Learning Events
Main data types	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name • Professional affiliation / organisation • Sector or area of expertise • Country / geographic location • Professional role or position • Email address or other contact details • Notes on relevance for the workshop or MLE focus
Purpose of data collection	Common database to be shared within the consortium to allow invitation waves for the MLEs

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/17198972>

Format and storage	Data were stored in a structured Excel spreadsheet (.xlsx) on SharePoint. Microsoft OneDrive, restricted SharePoint. Access is restricted to project team members responsible for workshop organisation and reporting. No personal data are stored on personal devices
Data management	Names, affiliations, and other identifying information are not included in research outputs unless explicit written consent is obtained. By default, contributions are anonymized in publications, reports, and datasets
Reuse and sharing	No personal data of experts (names, affiliations, email addresses) will be shared with third parties or deposited in open repositories. Any datasets resulting from the workshops will contain only anonymized or pseudonymized information.

4.2.1 MLEs dataset reusability after the end of the project

The expert contact data collected for the workshops are not intended for reuse after the end of the action. As the dataset contains personal and identifying information (names, affiliations, and contact details), it will not be shared externally or deposited in any repository. The data will be deleted in accordance with the project's retention schedule and GDPR requirements. Only fully anonymised, aggregate information on participant profiles (e.g., sector or geographic distribution) may be reused for reporting or evaluation purposes, without any possibility of identifying individuals.

4.3 Training modules dataset

The Training Modules dataset encompasses the complete collection of training courses developed and delivered, collectively forming the PATTERN training catalogue. This dataset is implemented within the OpenPlato Moodle learning management system and primarily consists of SCORM-based training modules.

The training modules are co-created by thematic leaders and subject-matter experts under WP2 and are subsequently deployed, piloted, and evaluated under WP3 across fourteen pilot organizations. Alongside the SCORM learning packages (OpenPlato e-learning catalogue), the dataset is supported by coordination and monitoring materials from WP2/WP3, which are stored in the project SharePoint. This includes supporting documents, monitoring spreadsheets, calendars, and ongoing meeting notes. Together, these elements comprise a structured and reusable dataset that documents both the training content and the context of its implementation within the PATTERN project.

Aspect	Description
Data origin	Training content and training designs were jointly developed by thematic leaders in collaboration with pilot organizations
Main data types	Self-paced SCORM courses (OpenPlato e-learning catalogue), interactive exercises, quizzes and train-the-trainer guides; session plans, case studies,

	metadata exercises, PID workflows and evaluation forms; documents, slide decks and translated materials
Purpose of data collection	To build OS/RRI competencies across researchers, support staff and citizen scientists; to provide evidence-based training aligned with EU policies; to provide training on transferable skills to multiple audiences
Format and storage	Materials are stored in OpenPlato (primary Large Learning Management System, LMS) as SCORM packages and structured learning paths; Projects platform hosts problem-based assignments and collaborative outputs; SharePoint (WP2-WP3 joint workspace) is used internally for scripts, drafts and versioning; Zenodo used for long-term FAIR preservation and DOI assignment. Main formats include .ppt and .pdf
Data management	Metadata visibility and FAIR compliance ensured through OpenAIRE integration
Reuse and sharing	Published under open licenses (CC-BY) to facilitate reuse and localization. Materials are accessible via OpenPlato and preserved on Zenodo, allowing researchers and institutions worldwide to download and reuse SCORM packages or single assets

4.3.1 Training modules dataset reusability after the end of the project

The training modules include different items that can be reused by other teachers, such as presentations, quizzes and teacher guidelines. Since all the material in PATTERN is published with a permissive Creative Commons licence, they can be treated as Open Educational Resources. The way in which they can be reused is either by downloading material from Zenodo and adjusting it to local needs, or by accessing OpenPlato and taking material that is hosted and published there, up to and including a whole SCORM package of a course.

4.4 Platforms dataset

The PATTERN project relies on two main platforms: the LPI Projects platform, which support project-based learning, and OpenAIRE's OpenPlato e-learning platform, which is based on Moodle 5.7 and has a Learning Management System. Platforms share a unified user accounts database, enabling "single-sign-on" between Projects and Open Plato.

PROJECTS PLATFORM	
Aspect	Description
Data origin	Data provided by learners during the trainings and the learning projects
Main data types	Courses and case studies on ORRI themes
Purpose of data collection	Document the learnings of users and share useful case studies with the ORRI community
Format and storage	Text, images and videos on the web Projects platform

Data management	Information is provided and controlled by the learners, who can opt out and ask for complete removal, following GDPR regulations
Reuse and sharing	Data is licensed under creative commons (with attribution, no commercial use) unless specified otherwise by the learners
OPENPLATO PLATFORM	
Aspect	Description
Data origin	Dataset produced through course configuration, content deployment, and learner-trainer interactions, captured systematically within Moodle's database
Main data types	System-generated and administrator-managed data, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Course and content metadata (course titles, categories, formats, SCORM activities, learning paths) • User and cohort data (user accounts, roles, enrolments, cohorts, access permissions) • Learning activity data (course participation, SCORM completion, quiz attempts, grades, timestamps) • Engagement and interaction logs (views, clicks, session duration, activity access) • Monitoring and performance data (course overview reports, statistics, completion tracking) • Operational and technical logs (system logs, live logs, error logs, antivirus checks, backups) • Evaluation and feedback data generated through activity usage and reporting tools
Purpose of data collection	To support operational management, specifically: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor course delivery and content availability • Track user participation, progress, and completion • Analyze engagement patterns and interaction levels • Support quality assurance and impact evaluation of training modules • Generate evidence for KPIs, monitoring & evaluation activities, and project reporting • Ensure controlled access, role management, and compliance with project requirements
Format and storage	All platform-level data are stored within OpenPlato's Moodle database. Data are accessed via administrative reporting tools (Analytics dashboards, User management interfaces, SCORM tracking). File-system storage is managed via Moodle's internal architecture, not direct access
Data management	Handled through Moodle's native administration tools allowing authorized administrators to control roles, monitor progress, review logs, and manage backups. Supports longitudinal analysis of training delivery
Reuse and sharing	Primarily intended for internal project use (coordination and monitoring). Aggregated and anonymised insights may be reused for reporting. The use of a standard open-

	source LMS (Moodle) ensures interoperability and institutional reuse of configurations
--	--

4.4.1 Platforms dataset reusability after the end of the project

Case studies, courses and problems created by teachers and implementations by students are reusable for future courses. The platforms will remain open and readable for at least 5 years. However, they are compliant with GDPR; in particular, students can choose to remove any assets they uploaded at any time. Copies of case studies that were already reused in other courses will remain open. All project data can be extracted through APIs, with the same right restrictions. By the end of year 2025, all data will also be available through MCP protocol, making it easy to exploit the data through LLMs and AI agents. This is important for long term reusability of the data, as Artificial Agents become more common in higher education and research.

With regards to OpenPlato, the PATTERN e-learning courses and associated SCORM packages can be maintained, updated, duplicated, or re-deployed within the platform or exported for reuse in other Moodle-compliant environments, ensuring technical interoperability and portability. OpenPlato's administrative tools enable ongoing management of course content, users, cohorts, and engagement data, allowing institutions and trainers to continue monitoring learning activities and adapting training materials to new audiences.

By choosing these platforms for the dissemination of our materials, PATTERN can guarantee that they remain continuously available e-learning service rather than a project-bound platform, because both platforms ensure the long-term accessibility, adaptability, and reuse of the PATTERN training ecosystem beyond the project lifetime.

4.5 Training plans dataset

The dataset comprises per-pilot calendars. Each plan lists event dates, topics, formats, target personas (R1-R4 researchers, support staff, community groups) and collaborating partners.

Aspect	Description
Data origin	Training plans of Learning Cycle 1 (LC1) and Learning Cycle 2 (LC2) co-developed by the 14 pilot organizations
Main data types	Schedules of training events (dates, duration, modality), event descriptions, target personas, and variety in delivery formats. Plans also note collaborating partners and cross-thematic links
Purpose of data collection	To provide a harmonized calendar of all training activities in LC1 and LC2, ensuring coordinated delivery across pilots and avoiding thematic overlap. Plans also allow WP3 to monitor participation, adjust resources, and support cross-institutional synergies
Format and storage	Finalized implementation plans are consolidated in D3.2 (PDF format/Zenodo). Operational data is managed via

	Excel-based monitoring sheets (.xlsx) on the internal SharePoint and a shared calendar for coordination (consortium level)
Data management	Raw data and supporting information (coordination details, organizational plans and exchanges) managed internally to the consortium; refined data for public documents (i.e. D3.1, D3.2)
Reuse and sharing	D3.2 and D3.1 are publicly accessible documents, available open source on Zenodo. The modular nature of the plans allows other institutions to replicate event structures while integrating their own case studies and languages

4.5.1 Training plans dataset reusability after the end of the project

As the training plans are tailored to the specific needs and academic/national contexts of the 14 pilot organizations, formal reusability measures for the raw data are limited. However, consolidated plans available in D3.1 and D3.2 are accessible on Zenodo (and will be available on the CORDIS repository upon approval). These documents serve as inspirational models for other organizations interested in upskilling their research communities in Open RRI transferable skills, providing a replicable framework for planning similar initiatives.

4.6 Piloting dataset

The PATTERN project's piloting dataset records the training activities undertaken by the fourteen pilot organisations during LC1 and LC2. Each pilot co-developed a training plan that outlines internal events (for its own researchers) and public events (open to wider communities). WP3 collects these plans using a standardized template and coordinates them through the PATTERN calendar.

Aspect	Description
Data origin	The dataset originates from the implementation of specific training activities scheduled and designed in the 14 personalized training plans (see paragraph above) for the pilot organizations
Main data types	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event metadata: event title, date/time, duration, delivery mode (webinar, workshop, bootcamp, summer school, self-paced course), thematic area(s) and personas targeted. • Participant data: expected number of participants (often estimated ranges), persona category (R1–R4). • Event classification: whether the event is internal (restricted to a pilot's community) or public (open to national or international attendees).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resources: links to OpenPlato modules, Projects-platform PBL assignments and accompanying materials
Purpose of data collection	Tracking and reporting training activities delivered according to the training plans
Format and storage	Event data are recorded in a structured spreadsheet (.xlsx) synchronized with the PATTERN calendar and stored on the project SharePoint
Data management	WP3 aggregates and validates submissions from pilots, ensuring consistency in naming, dates and persona targeting. WP3 integrates the information into the central calendar and uses dashboards to monitor key metrics (number of events, participants reached, thematic coverage, balance of internal/public events). Personal data (e.g., participant names) are not stored; only counts or anonymized statistics are used, compliant with GDPR
Reuse and sharing	No need for public long-term archiving is considered.

4.6.1 Piloting dataset reusability after the end of the project

As this dataset primarily concerns the recording and monitoring of specific training activities, the raw data is not intended for direct reuse. Furthermore, as it may contain personal data (e.g., participant information), it is not subject to open reusability measures by default. However, anonymized and aggregated data derived from this dataset are integrated into public project materials. These insights can be exploited by future initiatives to understand successful methodologies, delivery modes, and resource implementation strategies in the context of Open RRI training.

4.7 Evaluation: facilitator reflection dataset

Under Task 3.3, ZSI continuously collected and stored data related to the evaluation of implemented trainings from different perspectives and following different criteria. The facilitator template is an online questionnaire completed by training facilitators, allowing to get a holistic view of the implementation of a given training and providing lessons learned.

Aspect	Description
Data origin	T3.3 evaluation of trainings and learning outcomes
Main data types	Questionnaire responses as .xlsx files
Purpose of data collection	Evaluation and documentation of trainings from facilitators' perspectives
Format and storage	.xlsx file stored on personal Google Drive and project repository (SharePoint), secured through restricted access
Data management	Restricted to consortium only
Reuse and sharing	Any of the collected data may be shared with the Granting Authority, upon request, for reporting, auditing, and

	monitoring purposes. Beyond that, no need for public long-term archiving is considered.
--	---

4.7.1 Evaluation: facilitator reflection dataset reusability after the end of the project

As this dataset may contain personal information, it will not be subject to any proper reuse (i.e. by a third party) or reusability measure for the long-term. Aggregated information will be provided in publicly available project deliverables (D3.3 *Evaluation of Outcomes and Refinement Strategy*, D3.4 *Final Evaluation and Summary of Training Programs*).

4.8 Evaluation: participant questionnaire dataset

Under Task 3.3, ZSI continuously collected and stored data related to the evaluation of implemented trainings from different perspectives and following different criteria. The participant questionnaire is an online questionnaire completed by training participants, allowing to assess their experience of the respective training.

Aspect	Description
Data origin	T3.3 evaluation of trainings and learning outcomes
Main data types	Questionnaire responses as .xlsx files
Purpose of data collection	Evaluation of trainings from participants' perspectives
Format and storage	.xlsx file stored on ZSI's internal repository and project repository (SharePoint) secured through restricted access
Data management	Restricted to consortium until the end of T3.3, then shared anonymously on public repository
Reuse and sharing	After making sure the data is anonymized, it will be shared on Zenodo by the end of T3.3 as a .csv file

4.8.1 Evaluation: participant questionnaire dataset reusability after the end of the project

The anonymised data will be published for reuse by third parties (e.g., researchers) after the project period under the latest Creative Commons Attribution license (currently CC-BY 4.0 International).

4.9 Evaluation: Interviews with pilot institutions

Under Task 3.3, ZSI continuously collected and stored data related to the evaluation of implemented trainings from different perspectives and following different criteria. ZSI also conducted qualitative interviews with representatives from pilot institutions, such as educational coordinators, to capture experiences, outcomes, challenges, and recommendations from an institutional perspective.

Aspect	Description
--------	-------------

Data origin	T3.3 evaluation of trainings and learning outcomes
Main data types	Audio and video recordings, transcripts
Purpose of data collection	Evaluation of trainings from institutional perspective
Format and storage	Recordings are stored as .mp4 files and transcripts as .docx files on ZSI's internal repository, secured through restricted access
Data management	Restricted to ZSI only
Reuse and sharing	Restricted to ZSI only: public long-term archiving serves no need since the dataset would lack context, as it is generated for internal use

4.9.1 Evaluation: Interviews with pilot institutions dataset reusability after the end of the project

As this dataset contains personal information and interview partners were recorded under the promise of anonymity, it will not be subject to any proper reuse (i.e. by a third party) or reusability measure for the long-term. Aggregated information will be provided in a publicly available project deliverable (D3.4).

4.10 Policy mapping dataset

Under WP4, Task 4.1, through state-of-the-art desk-analysis, ESF mapped existing initiatives, guidelines and policy frameworks featuring the trainings for Open Science and RRI practices in English, with a focus on assessing and identifying gaps and needs both at EU and national level. To this aim, a set of parameters and corresponding guiding questions related to each parameter to get evidence and directions for further national and institutional mapping exercises (mapping grids and reports) was developed. The results were consolidated in deliverable D4.1 (*State-of-the-art Analysis: Mapping of the Policy Landscape for Learning Opportunities*) that covers three levels of granularity: European Union (EU), national and institutional policies as well as in the deliverable D4.2 (*First PATTERN Policy Brief*), building on the policy mapping results.

Aspect	Description
Data origin	Existing policies at different levels: EU, national and institutional levels
Main data types	Policy mapping tool (mapping grids and narrative reports) - .xlsx, docx. files
Purpose of data collection	Draft of policy baseline analysis
Format and storage	.xlsx and docx. files stored on project repository (SharePoint) secured through restricted access
Data management	Managed according to project's DMP; access permissions restricted to project partners
Reuse and sharing	Public dissemination of conclusions in D4.1 and D4.2, via Zenodo

4.10.1 Policy mapping dataset reusability after the end of the project

The reusability of this dataset is limited, as the materials consist of internal working documents and preliminary assessments developed exclusively for project-internal analytical purposes. All relevant and publicly shareable findings have already been consolidated in Deliverable D4.1, which includes the list of EU-level policies and initiatives mapped, as well as the national and institutional policy mapping report templates. Therefore, the underlying dataset is not intended for reuse beyond the scope of the project.

4.11 Dissemination dataset

The main dissemination dataset generated during the PATTERN project concerns subscribers to the project newsletter collected via the project website. It includes a limited set of personal data, together with basic metadata such as subscription date, consent status and engagement metrics. The dataset is managed through a GDPR-compliant email marketing platform and is used exclusively for sending project updates, event announcements and related communication materials to interested stakeholders. Data processing is based on explicit, documented consent and strictly follows data protection principles of minimisation, purpose limitation and storage limitation. No raw personal data are made public or shared outside the consortium. Only aggregated and fully anonymised statistics derived from this dataset are used for reporting, impact assessment and future proposal development.

Aspect	Description
Data origin	Newsletter subscription form on the project website (linked to Zoho campaigns “.eu” which has servers in the Netherlands and Switzerland)
Main data types	Personal data: First name; Last name; Email; Organization. Metadata: subscription date/ time; consent record; unsubscribe status; bounce status; basic engagement metrics (opens/ clicks)
Purpose of data collection	To manage the project newsletter mailing list; send project news, event invitations and updates; monitor communication KPIs (e.g. number of subscribers, open and click rates) for project reporting; ensure that only users who have explicitly opted in receive communications
Format and storage	Primarily stores in Zoho Campaigns’ database (cloud-based, GDPR-compliant with servers located in Switzerland, the Netherlands with a backup centre in Dublin). Periodic exports in CSV/ XLSX format stored on LOBA drive
Data management	Access restricted to LOBA staff only. Data processed on the legal basis of explicit consent (double opt-in). Data quality maintained through periodic list cleaning (removing bounces and inactive contacts). Retention: kept until users unsubscribe or max. 5 years after project end (until project website is kept live by LOBA), then deleted. Subject rights (access, rectification, erasure) handled via unsubscribe link embedded in every email distribution

Reuse and sharing	Raw personal data are not shared outside the Consortium and are not published as open data due to GDPR constraints. Only aggregated, anonymized statistics (e.g. number of subscribers by country, open/ click rates) are reused for project deliverables, reports, presentations and possibly future proposals
--------------------------	---

4.11.1 Dissemination dataset reusability after the end of the project

Because of its nature and purpose, this dataset is not suitable for re-use or publication as open or shared data after the end of the action. The information it contains is strictly covered by GDPR and consent was obtained only for receiving project communication, not for any broader or future re-use of the raw data. For this reason, the subscriber list will not be deposited in any repository, shared with third parties outside the consortium, or made available under an open licence.

After the project ends, personal data will either be deleted or, where relevant for institutional reporting, reduced to fully anonymised and aggregated statistics. These statistics do not constitute a reusable research dataset and will only be used internally for reporting and impact assessment.

4.12 Management dataset

Under WP6, PATTERN continuously collected and stored data related to project management, coordination procedures, monitoring and reporting activities. This dataset is essential for ensuring a smooth implementation of the project.

Data is gathered from a variety of project management actions, including:

- Recurrent and ad-hoc meetings
- Preparation and submission of project deliverables
- Continuous and periodic reporting of the project, including financial assessment
- Everyday communication among consortium members

Aspect	Description
Data origin	Tasks 6.1-6.3 regarding project management and coordination
Main data types	Meetings' agendas and recordings, presentations, deliverables, reporting documentation, contacts, guidelines, contracts and admin documents
Purpose of data collection	To ensure smooth project coordination, and a proper completion of all project's activities; project reporting; to comply with the Grant Agreement obligations in terms of Record Keeping
Format and storage	PDF and .docx files; .pptx presentations; .xlsx lists and monitoring documents; mp4 recordings; all stored in project's repository (SharePoint), secured through restricted access

Data management	Restricted to consortium only; APRE manages the project's SharePoint under its own IT tenant and infrastructure, while all consortium members have full access and editing rights to file and folders
Reuse and sharing	Any of the collected data may be shared with the Granting Authority, upon request, for reporting, auditing, and monitoring purposes

4.12.1 Management dataset reusability after the end of the project

Being mainly related to internal documents and procedures, this dataset will not be subject to any proper reuse (i.e. by a third party) or reusability measure for the long-term. Given its confidential nature and functional scope, only the Granting Authority might request for its reuse, for specific purposes.

5. Conclusions

The definition and implementation of the *Final Data Management Plan* mark a crucial moment in the PATTERN project's data strategy. As the action implementation approaches the last six months of its duration, the Consortium has successfully moved from a theoretical application of the FAIR principles to the practical, consolidated management of 12 distinct datasets.

As detailed in this document, the data management strategy has achieved two primary objectives, ensuring that the project's digital legacy persists well beyond its conclusion:

1. **Sustainable Open Access:** high-value assets (mainly the training modules and public reports) have been secured as Open Educational Resources (OER). Their long-term availability is guaranteed not only by static repositories like Zenodo but also by the resilience of the project's digital ecosystem. Since OpenPlato and the Projects Platform operate as independent infrastructures, unrelated to the project's administrative lifespan, they ensure that the Training Modules (Dataset 4.3) and Platform Data (Dataset 4.4) remain technically accessible and interoperable for future learners and researchers.
2. **Compliance and Security:** strictly confidential data, including sensitive qualitative interviews (Dataset 4.10) and personal stakeholder information, have been managed in full compliance with GDPR. The "Exit Strategy" for these datasets ensures their secure deletion or anonymization, guaranteeing that no privacy risks persist after the grant ends.

In conclusion, this DMP confirms that PATTERN's data lifecycle is designed for longevity. By leveraging robust, independent platforms for preservation and adhering to strict ethical standards for sensitive data, the project ensures that its generated knowledge remains a permanent, open resource for the European Research Area.

PATTERN.

Empowering Open and Responsible
Research and Innovation

OUR CONSORTIUM

OpenAIRE
affiliated entities

Funded by
the European Union

pattern-openresearch.eu

info@pattern-openresearch.eu